

Appraising the Cost and Economic Returns of White Yam (*Dioscorea rotundata* Prior) Cultivation in Umuagwo, South-eastern Nigeria

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Abstract: Field experiment was conducted at Teaching and Demonstration Farm of University of Agriculture and Environmental Sciences, Umuagwo, Imo State, Nigeria, to appraise the cost and economic returns of three elite yam varieties. The treatments were three elite yam varieties (UMUDr33, UMUDr34, and UMUDr36) and Abi (a local variety) as a control treatment. The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design, replicated three times. Data were collected on yield parameters. In all yam varieties, the highest production cost was associated with three weeding operations (3x), amounting to ₦ 278,000, by the cost of yam seeds (planting materials), which was ₦ 235,000 for the local variety and ₦ 250,000 for the UMUDr 33, UMUDr 34, and UMUDr 36 varieties, respectively. The cost of land preparation for all yam varieties was recorded at ₦ 125,000. Harvesting costs were ranked fourth at ₦ 102,000, while staking incurred a cost of ₦ 100,000, placing it fifth in the ranking of field operations. Comparing the varieties, UMUDr 36 stood out significantly, achieving the highest gross revenue of ₦ 5,784,000. The UMUDr 36 variety had a net revenue of ₦ 4,515,300, underscoring its profitability for farmers. The cost/benefit ratio for UMUDr 36 was an impressive ₦ 3.56, which indicates that for every N 1 spent on production, farmers earned ₦3.56 in return, highlighting the variety's exceptional economic value of UMUDr 36. The UMUDr 36 strongly recommends to farmers in Umuagwo for high yield and economic returns.

Keywords: *Economic Returns, Cost of Production, Yam Varieties, Yield.*

Introduction

White yam (*Dioscorea rotundata*) is a significant species in Nigeria and other regions of West Africa, where its vines are typically trained to grow on sturdy stakes. In West Africa, *Dioscorea rotundata*, commonly known as white yam or white guinea yam, is the most extensively cultivated specie. It serves as a vital source of food and income for millions of producers, processors, and consumers. Yam plays an essential role in the livelihoods of those within the yam belt of Nigeria and other West African nations (Mondo et al., 2024).

Nigeria stands as the world's leading producer of yam, accounting for approximately 81% of Africa's production and contributing to 70-76% of global yam output annually. In 2023, the country produced over 18.3 million tonnes of yams across 1.5 million hectares. The highest contributions come from Benue State, which is responsible for 51% of the total yam cultivation in Nigeria, followed by Taraba State, which contributes about 13% (IITA, 2024).

According to a study conducted by the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS), yam ranks as the most widely harvested crop in

Nigeria, following cassava, maize, sorghum, and cowpea. However, current yam production significantly falls short of meeting the increasing demand. One of the primary challenges faced by yam farmers is the high cost and limited availability of quality yam seeds. The expense associated with procuring these seeds hampers farmers' ability to expand their production. Additionally, the inconsistent supply of seeds complicates access for farmers even further (NBS, 2024)

Moreover, the high labour costs associated with harvesting and marketing present a significant challenge. The labour-intensive nature of yam farming contributes to elevated operational expenses. Investing in mechanization and implementing government initiatives aimed at reducing labor costs could alleviate this burden on farmers. Additionally, yam cultivation in Nigeria faces threats from various pests and diseases, including termites, millipedes, crickets, nematodes, the yam mosaic virus, and yam rots. These biological challenges not only reduce yields but also compromise the quality of the harvested tubers.(Ikeh and Ndaeyo, 2021).

Yam, particularly white yam, holds significant cultural, social, economic, and

religious values in many African societies (Obidiegwu et al., 2020; Ikeh et al., 2023). It is regarded as a prestigious food crop in various African communities, especially among the Igbo tribes in Nigeria, where yam plays a central role in numerous traditional celebrations. Ceremonies related to yam planting and harvesting, such as “Ahojoku” in Igbo land, are significant annual social and religious events (Ikeh and Ndaeyo, 2021). In the Ugep community of Cross River State, Nigeria, the celebration of the new yam festival, known as ‘Leboku,’ has achieved international recognition and serves as a vital source of income for the state. Additionally, yam is integral to many traditional marriage ceremonies and is included in special diets for mothers during confinement after childbirth (Ikeh and Ndaeyo, 2021). No other crop in Nigeria or Africa overall is more deeply connected to social and cultural activities than yam (Ikeh et al., 2012). The significance of yams in Nigeria is attributed to their high calorie content and socio-cultural importance, which helps to explain their rising cost, as production has not kept pace with demand (Sun et al., 2024).

Despite the significant role of yam in Nigeria's farming systems, its yield is consistently declining, primarily due to low

productivity linked to pests and diseases, particularly in southeastern Nigeria. This decline is exacerbated by limited agricultural land caused by urbanization, a steadily growing population, and other factors such as the degeneration of popular varieties, increasing pest pressures (both field and storage pests), and various diseases (including nematodes, mealybugs, scales, anthracnose, and viruses). Additionally, farmers face high tuber losses during storage, elevated costs for staking materials and labor, as well as the scarcity and high prices of clean (pest- and disease-free) planting materials.

In light of these challenges, farmers have increasingly viewed yam as less viable for income generation compared to other root and tuber crops in Nigeria. However, in 2024, the International Institute of Tropical Agriculture (IITA–CGIAR), in collaboration with the National Root Crops Research Institute (NRCRI), introduced several promising improved yam varieties: UMUDr33, UMUDr34, and UMUDr36. This breakthrough, driven by research findings, has the potential to address the issue of low yields in Nigeria's yam-producing regions.

According to an IITA report (2024), these newly released yam varieties are considered to be elite or superior compared to the existing varieties and landraces throughout the yam belts of Nigeria. Consequently, this study was conducted to evaluate the cost and economic viability of these promising yam varieties within the rainforest ecology of southeastern Nigeria.

Materials and Methods

Description of the Study Area

The experiment was carried out at Teaching and Research Farm of University of Agriculture and Environmental Sciences (UAES), Umuagwo, Imo state, Nigeria. Umuagwo is located on the latitudes 5°18' 21 – 5°30' 58 N and longitudes 6°56' 44 - 6°94' 56 E. The area belongs to the low-lying part of southeastern Nigeria, and soils are derived from Coastal Plain Sands and shale. Rainforest vegetation is dominant in the area while it has a humid tropical climate. Total mean annual rainfall is between 1800 and 2500 mm, and is bimodal, with long (March - July) and short (September – November) rainy seasons. The annual temperature ranges from 26 to 30 °C. The land in the inland valley of Otamiri stream had reliable available water from the stream or groundwater, which maintained soil

moisture content of the experimental site. The experimental site is well known for dry-season vegetable crop research.

The predominant weeds observed in the Teaching and Research Farm of University of Agriculture and Environmental Sciences, Umuagwo, before planting were; elephant grass (*Pennisetum purpurem*), giant star grass (*Cynodon plectostachyus*), African marigold (*Asprilia africana*) wild groundnut (*Calopogonium mucunoides*), butterfly pea (*Centrosema pubescens*), siam weed (*Chromolaena odorata*), and goat weed (*Sida acuta*).

Experimental Design, layout and treatments

The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design (RCBD). The treatment was replicated three times. The experiment occupied a land area of 30 m x 30 m. Each plot size was 6m x 6m (36m²) with a space of 1m between each plot and 1.5m between blocks.

The experimental treatments were four yam varieties (UMUDr33, UMUDr34 and UMUDr36 and local adaptable yam cultivar-*Abi* as control).

Source of planting materials:

The improved yam varieties (UMUDr33, UMUDr34 and UMUDr36) were obtained from traditional barn of International Institute of Tropical Agriculture (IITA), Ibadan, Oyo State. while popular local cultivar- Abi was obtained from Eke Umuagwo market in Umuagwo, Ohaji/Egbema local government of Imo state, Nigeria.

Agronomic Practices

Land Preparation:

The site was manually cleared with machetes and a spade. The land was prepared into ridges with the aid of a spade and Indian hoes.

Planting:

Planting was done in November 2024. The sett size of 300g was planted on ridges at 1m x1m spacing.

Mulching

Yam field was mulched immediately after land preparation. Grasses were used as mulching materials. The mulching materials were gathered within the Teaching and Research Farm of the University of Agriculture and Environmental Sciences, Umuagwo, Imo State., Nigeria.

Irrigation:

The yam field was irrigated twice per week. The rudimentary irrigation was done during the evening with the aid of a watering can. The irrigation commenced immediately after planting and stopped when rainfall started in March 2025.

Source of Irrigation Water:

Water for irrigation was collected from the Otamiri stream within the Teaching and Research Farm of the University of Agriculture and Environmental Sciences, Umuagwo.

Staking:

Staking was done when the yam shoots were 1m long. The pyramid staking method was used. Bamboo sticks was used as staking materials.

Weeding:

Manual hoeing was done two (2) months after planting (MAP), while slashing of the yam field will be done at five (5) (MAP).

Harvesting:

Harvesting of yam tubers took place at seven (7) months after planting (MAP). The tubers were manually harvested using an iron dibber. Maximum care and precaution were taken during the harvesting process to

avoid contamination and ensure accurate data collection. During the operation, net plots were carefully marked. All harvested tubers from each plot were gathered at the harvesting site and labeled to facilitate relevant harvest data collection and proper storage of the tubers after data collection.

Data Collection and Analysis

The data collected from growth, yield, and yield components were subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA) according to the procedure for a randomized complete block design using GENSTAT Discovery Edition 3 Statistical Package (2012). The comparison of the treatment means for significance was done by the use of least significant difference (LSD) procedure at 5% level of probability.

The cost and economic returns to management was determined using the partial budgeting method of with the following descriptions:

- a) Total Cost of Production (TCP)
- b) Gross Revenue from sales of yam tubers (GR)
- c) Net Revenue (NR) = TCP-GR
- d) Cost/Benefit Ratio = NR/TCP

Results

The Cost and Ranking of Field Operations Associated with Cultivation of Yam in Umuagwo

Table 1 presents the cost of yam production in Umuagwo for various yam varieties on a per-hectare basis. Across all yam varieties, the highest production cost was associated with three weeding operations (3x), amounting to N 278,000. This was followed by the cost of yam seeds (planting materials), which was N 235,000 for the local variety Abi and N 250,000 for the UMUDr 33, UMUDr 34, and UMUDr 36 varieties, respectively. The cost of land preparation for all yam varieties was recorded at N 125,000. Harvesting costs were ranked fourth at N 102,000, while staking incurred a cost of N 100,000, placing it fifth in the ranking of field operations. The cost of irrigation was N 67,500, ranked sixth, and labor costs for staking amounted to N 56,800, securing the seventh position. The cost of mulching materials was N 40,000, ranked eighth, and the purchase of 40 bags of poultry manure also cost N 40,000, taking the ninth position. Planting yam seeds was ranked tenth with a cost of N 30,000 per hectare. Lastly, the cost of applying poultry manure in the field was N 22,300, which was ranked eleventh

among all production costs considered within the Umugwo agro-ecology.

Table 1 Cost and Ranking of Field Operations Associated with Off-Season Cultivation of Yam in Umuagwo

Cost of Production/Hectare	N/ha				Rank
	UMUDr 33	UMUDr 34	UMUDr 36	Abi	
Soil Analysis	20,000	20,000	20,000	20,000	12 th
Land preparations	125,000	125,000	125,000	125,000	3 rd
Yam Seeds	250,000	250,000	250,000	235,000	2 nd
Planting	30,000	30,000	30,000	30,000	10 th
Mulching materials	45,000	45,000	45,000	45,000	8 th
Irrigation	67,500	67,500	67,500	67,500	6 th
Weeding (3x)	278,000	278,000	278,000	278,000	1 st
Staking Materials	100,000	100,000	100,000	100,000	5 th
Staking	56,800	56,800	56,800	56,800	7 th
Poultry Manure (40 bags)	40,000	40,000	40,000	40,000	9 th
Poultry manure application	22,300	22,300	22,300	22,300	11 th
Harvesting	102,000	102,000	102,000	102,000	4 th
TCP	1,268,700	1,268,700	1,268,700	1,152,200	

Yield and Yield Components

The impact of yam varieties on the number of seed tubers per plant is shown in Table 2. The variety UMUDr 36 yielded a significantly higher average of 2.18 seed tubers per plant. Following closely, UMUDr 33 produced 2.10 seed tubers, while UMUDr 34 recorded only 1.01 seed tubers. The local variety, Abi, had the lowest yield with 1.01 seed tubers per plant.

Additionally, the number of ware tubers per plant varied significantly among the different varieties ($p < 0.05$), with UMUDr 36 generating 1.18 ware tubers, whereas no ware tubers were observed in the local variety.

Tuber yields, as influenced by the varieties, also exhibited significant differences

($p < 0.05$) as shown in Table 2. Yam variety (UMUDr 36) achieved a commendable tuber yield of 38.54 t/ha, followed by UMUDr 33 with 33.60 t/ha. The yield recorded in UMUDr 34 was 28.65 t/ha, while the least

yield was recorded at 15.79 t/ha for the local variety. The results indicate that UMUDr 36 provided a tuber yield that was 13-59% higher compared to the other varieties.

Table 2 Number of Tubers per Plant and Tuber Yield as Influenced by Yam Varieties

Yam Varieties	Number of Seed tubers/ plant	Number of Ware tubers/ plant	Total Number of Tubers /Plant	Tuber Yield (t/ha)
UMUDr 33	2.10	1.01	3.11	33.60
UMUDr 34	1.01	1.41	2.42	28.65
UMUDr 36	2.18	1.18	3.36	38.54
Abi	1.01	0.00	1.01	15.79
LSD($p < 0.05$)	1.21	0.69	1.46	4.53

Economic Returns to Management

The gross revenue generated from yam sales is thoroughly summarized in Table 3, showcasing the financial performance of various yam varieties cultivated by farmers. Among the varieties, UMUDr 36 variety stood out significantly, achieving the highest gross revenue of N 5,784,000. This remarkable performance translated to a net revenue of N 4,515,300, underscoring its profitability for farmers. The cost/benefit ratio for UMUDr 36 was an impressive N 3.56, which indicates that for every N 1 spent on production, farmers earned N 3.56 in return, highlighting the variety's exceptional economic value.

Following closely, the UMUDr 33 variety generated a gross revenue of N 5,040,000, resulting in a net revenue of N 3,771,300. This variety's cost/benefit ratio was calculated at N 2.97, suggesting that farmers could expect nearly N 3 for every N 1 invested in its cultivation.

In contrast, the UMUDr 34 variety reported a gross revenue of N 4,297,500 coupled with a net revenue of N 3,028,800. While it generated a lower gross income, it still provided a respectable cost/benefit ratio of 2.39, indicating that for every N 1 spent on farm operations, farmers received N 2.39 in

return. Overall, these figures illustrate the varying financial outcomes associated with different yam varieties and demonstrate the potential for farmers to enhance their

profitability through informed crop selection. The least economic returns was recorded in local variety.

Table 3 Economic Returns to Management from Different Yam Varieties

Returns From Yam Varieties	N/ha			
	UMUDr 33	UMUDr 34	UMUDr 36	Abi
Tuber Yield(t/ha)	33.60	28.65	38.56	15.79
Gross Revenue (GR)	5,040,000	4,297,500	5,784,000	2,368,500
Net Revenue (NR)	3,771,300	3,028,800	4,515,300	1,216,300
Cost/ Benefit Ratio	2.97	2.39	3.56	1.06

NB: Cost of a tonne of white yam tuber during harvesting, based on the farm gate Price was N 150,000

Discussion

The results of the study revealed significant variations in both yield and yield components among different yam varieties, indicating that improved varieties consistently outperformed local landrace varieties. Notably, the improved variety UMUDr 36 exhibited the highest tuber yield, followed closely by UMUDr 33 and UMUDr 34. In stark contrast, the local variety recorded the least tuber yield, which may be attributed to the minimal genetic improvement associated with traditional landraces. The observed yield variations among the improved yam varieties can also be ascribed to the distinct inherent genetic makeup of the various yam genotypes, as reported by Maurice and Akata (2022).

Furthermore, Ikeh et al. (2021) highlighted significant variations among different yam cultivars specifically cultivated in kaolinitic Ultisols in Southeastern Nigeria, underscoring the importance of soil type in agricultural output.

Additionally, the study revealed that the cost of weed control constituted the largest proportion of expenses incurred during yam cultivation in Umuagwo, followed by the cost of planting materials (seed yams) and land preparation, which ranked as the second and third most significant expenses, respectively. The total production costs ranged from ₦1,152,200 for the local variety to ₦1,268,700 for the improved varieties.

Although the overall cost of production was relatively high across all farming operations, higher income levels were also achieved, particularly with UMUDr 36, which yielded an impressive return of ₦3.56 for every ₦1 spent in cultivating the crop. This finding aligns with the report by Amusa et al. (2018), which documented total revenues of ₦230,590.00 and a Gross Margin (GM) of ₦88,390.00 from yam cultivation in Umudike, Umuahia, Abia State, Nigeria.

Moreover, the study indicated that yam varieties especially UMUDr 36 cultivated in Umuagwo yielded high and had higher economic returns compared to the net revenue of ₦86,585.00 and a Profitable Index (PI) of 0.38 reported by Amusa et al. (2018). The yield and profit margins realized from yam production in Umuagwo affirm the findings of IITA (2009), which stated that yam cultivation is a highly profitable agricultural enterprise, despite the challenges posed by high production costs and price fluctuations in the market. According to IITA (2009), the average profit per yam tuber after harvest and storage in most producing areas in Nigeria during peak harvest periods was estimated to exceed US\$13,000 per hectare, highlighting the economic potential of yam farming in the region.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The study's results revealed that the elite yam cultivars significantly tuber yields compared to the local variety known as Abi. They also had higher economic returns to farmers. Among the evaluated cultivars, UMUDr 36 stood out with the highest cost/benefit ratio, indicating it offered the best return on investment for cultivators. Following closely were UMUDr 33 and UMUDr 34, which also demonstrated favorable financial outcomes, while Abi recorded the lowest performance metrics in both yield and economic returns.

These findings suggest a clear advantage in adopting these elite cultivars. Therefore, the study strongly recommended that farmers in Umuagwo and its surrounding areas consider transitioning to the UMUDr 36, UMUDr 33, and UMUDr 34 cultivars. Such a shift not only promises greater tuber yields but also has the potential to significantly enhance their overall economic viability and sustainability in yam production.

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